

Clinical Research Co-Ordination

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Acronym matrix

Acronym	Full Form	Definition
4-HIAA	4-Hydroxyindole-3-Acetic Acid	A main product formed when serotonin is broken down in the body. It is also involved in the breakdown of psilocin.
5-HT2A	5-Hydroxytryptamine Receptor 2A	A type of serotonin receptor that affects mood and is involved in the effects of certain drugs, including psychedelics.
Breakthrough Therapy	Special regulatory designation	A status given to certain treatments that show great promise, allowing faster development and approval.
CNS	Central Nervous System	The part of the nervous system that includes the brain and spinal cord, responsible for controlling thoughts, movements, and functions.
COMP360	Psilocybin based drug	A type of drug being studied in clinical trials for therapy, especially in mental health treatments.
CYP	Cytochrome P450	A group of enzymes essential for breaking down COMP360 in the body.
DMN	Default Mode Network	A group of brain areas that work together when a person is not focusing on the outside world, often related to daydreaming or self-reflection.
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid	The molecule that carries the genetic information of all living things.
ECG	Electrocardiogram	A test that records the heart's electrical activity to help diagnose heart conditions.
EMA	European Medicines Agency	The organisation that checks and supervises medicines in the European Union to make sure they are safe and effective.
EUDA	European Union Drugs Agency	An agency that provides rules and information about drug use and regulations in the EU.
FDA	Food and Drug Administration	The US government agency that is responsible for ensuring that food and drugs are safe and effective.

GLP	Good Laboratory Practice	A set of standards used in laboratories to ensure that experiments are conducted correctly and that results are reliable.
ICH	International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use	A global group that creates guidelines to make sure drugs are safe and effective for people.
IKr	Rapid component of the delayed rectifier potassium current in cardiac cells	A type of electrical current in heart cells that helps regulate the heart's rhythm.
kg	Kilogram	A unit of mass in the metric system, equal to 1,000 grams.
MAO	Monoamine Oxidase	An enzyme that breaks down important chemicals in the brain, such as serotonin and dopamine.
mg/ml	Milligram per milliliter	A unit used to measure the concentration of a substance in a liquid.
mM	Millimolar	A unit of concentration, representing one millimole of a substance per litre of solution.
M3(R2)	ICH Guideline on Non-Clinical Safety Studies to Support Human Clinical Trials and Marketing Authorization	A guideline for safety studies done before clinical trials to make sure a drug is safe to test in humans.
µg	Microgram	A very small unit of mass equals one millionth of a gram.
µL	Microliter	A very small unit of volume equals one millionth of a litre.
NCT	National Clinical Trial	A unique identification number for clinical trials registered in the US.
NLM	National Library of Medicine	A US-based library that provides access to medical research, including journals and clinical studies.
OCD	Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder	A mental health condition where people have repeated, unwanted thoughts and behaviours that they feel they must perform.
PD	Pharmacodynamics	The study of how a drug affects the body, including its actions and effects.
Phase 2 Trial	Second stage of clinical trials	The phase in which a drug's effectiveness and correct dosage are tested on a small group of patients.

Phase 3 Trial	Third stage of clinical trials	The phase where a drug is tested on a large group of people to confirm its safety and effectiveness before approval.
PK	Pharmacokinetics	The study of how a drug moves through the body, including how it is absorbed, distributed, processed, and eliminated.
PTSD	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder	A mental health disorder that can develop after someone experiences or witnesses a life-threatening event, causing symptoms like flashbacks and anxiety.
QT	Time interval on an electrocardiogram (ECG) measuring heart rhythm	A measurement of the time it takes for the heart's electrical system to reset and prepare for the next heartbeat.
S2(R1)	ICH Guideline on Genotoxicity Studies	A guideline on testing a drug's potential harmful effects on genes, including mutations.
S7	ICH Guideline on Safety Pharmacology Studies	A guideline outlining the safety studies required to check if a drug has dangerous effects on the heart, nervous system, or other organs.
TRD	Treatment-Resistant Depression	A form of depression that does not improve with standard treatments, often requiring alternative or more intensive therapies.
UGT	UDP-Glucuronosyltransferases	A group of enzymes involved in the process of attaching glucuronic acid to drugs, helping to eliminate them from the body.

Introduction

COMP360 is an innovative psychedelic therapy based on synthetic psilocybin, currently in clinical development. Initial development focused on a single therapeutic indication – Treatment-Resistant Depression (TRD). As research progressed, the potential applications expanded to include other psychiatric conditions, leading to several clinical trials at various stages of development.

Current key studies for COMP360 include:

- » **Phase 2 clinical trial** (NCT03775200) – evaluating the efficacy and safety of different doses of COMP360 in treating TRD.
- » **Phase 3 clinical trial** (NCT05711940 & NCT05624268) – two parallel trials investigating the long-term efficacy and safety of COMP360 in patients with TRD.
- » **Study of COMP360 for the treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD)** (NCT05312151) – preliminary studies evaluating the potential therapeutic benefits.
- » **Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) study** (NCT04656301) – analysing the effect of COMP360 on OCD symptoms in combination with supportive therapy.

Despite the advanced stage of clinical trials, COMP360 has not yet been approved for marketing, so it does not have a European Medicines Agency (EMA) assessment report available on the official EMA website. However, many scientific publications, reports, and summaries are available on completed clinical trials of both COMP360 and psilocybin itself.

Psilocybin, the active ingredient in COMP360, is a psychoactive substance naturally occurring in over 200 species of mushrooms, commonly known as “magic mushrooms”. Its use in healing rituals dates back thousands of years, but in the 20th century, it was classified as an illegal substance. Modern scientific research is rediscovering the therapeutic potential of this substance, leading to a revision of earlier information about it and opening up new possibilities for its use in medicine.

The rapid development of research on COMP360 and other psychedelic therapies suggests that these substances may play a significant role in the treatment of psychiatric disorders in the future. Groundbreaking discoveries in this field may lead to a change in the approach to the treatment of mental disorders, emphasising the need for further research on the mechanisms of action and the safety of psilocybin in controlled clinical settings.

COMP360 (Psilocybin) drug overview and description

As we can read on the sponsor's website for the COMP360 trials (Compass Pathways Editor, 2025), COMP360 is an experimental treatment currently undergoing clinical trials for mental health conditions, mainly focusing on treatment-resistant depression (TRD). This therapy uses a synthetic form of psilocybin, a psychedelic compound, to treat conditions that are difficult to address with conventional medications. TRD represents a significant challenge, as patients fail to respond adequately to standard antidepressants. The development of COMP360 aims to address this gap in treatment, with additional studies also exploring its potential for conditions like post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and anorexia nervosa. The positive results from early trials have generated significant interest, leading to COMP360 being granted Breakthrough Therapy status by regulatory bodies. This designation underscores the need for more effective treatments for conditions like TRD and highlights the potential of COMP360 to make a transformative impact on psychiatric care.

TRD is characterised by insufficient improvement in symptoms despite multiple antidepressant treatments. It poses a serious issue for both patients and healthcare systems, often resulting in prolonged suffering, reduced functionality, and a higher risk of suicide. New treatments are urgent, as many patients struggle with existing therapies. Clinical trials have shown that COMP360 could offer a promising alternative. A Phase 2b study found that a 25mg dose of COMP360, when combined with psychological support, led to a significant reduction in depressive symptoms compared to a very low 1mg dose. These results were confirmed by a follow-up study (COMP004), published in the March edition of *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* (Goodwin *et al.*, 2025), which showed that the 25mg dose produced long-lasting antidepressant effects in some participants, lasting up to 12 weeks. Based on these encouraging findings, a Phase 3 clinical program has been launched, marking the largest clinical trial of psilocybin for TRD. This progression demonstrates the growing confidence in COMP360's potential to meet the significant needs of TRD patients.

As we can learn from various clinical studies published on platforms such as the (European Medicines Agency, 2025) and the (National Library of Medicine, 2025), COMP360 is also being investigated for its potential to treat other mental health conditions. Preliminary research, including a Phase 2 study, suggests that COMP360 could help alleviate symptoms of PTSD. One open-label study observed significant and sustained improvements in PTSD symptoms after COMP360 administration. These findings suggest that psilocybin may play a role in emotional processing and regulation, which could be beneficial for conditions related to trauma.

COMP360 is also being tested in individuals with anorexia nervosa through ongoing Phase 2 trials. These studies are evaluating its effects on quality of life, psychosocial functioning, anxiety, and depression. Since eating disorders often co-occur with mood disorders, the antidepressant effects of COMP360 may offer additional benefits to patients with anorexia.

The active substance in COMP360 is psilocybin, a naturally occurring psychedelic compound found in over 200 species of mushrooms, often referred to as „magic mushrooms” (European Union Drugs Agency (EUDA), 2025). Psilocybin belongs to the tryptamine family, and its chemical structure closely resembles that of serotonin, a neurotransmitter that regulates mood and behaviour. Psilocybin is a prodrug converted into its active form, psilocin, in the body. This conversion takes place primarily in the gastrointestinal tract and liver, where psilocybin is dephosphorylated into psilocin, which then affects the brain.

As noted by (Goodwin *et al.*, 2023), COMP360 is a synthetic form of psilocybin developed to allow precise control over its purity and dosage. This controlled formulation is essential for clinical trials. COMP360 is usually administered orally in the form of a capsule under the supervision of trained therapists who provide psychological support during treatment. The combination of pharmacological therapy and psychological guidance is central to the approach, helping to shape the patient's experience and maximise the therapeutic effects.

PD (Pharmacodynamics)

Psilocin interacts with serotonin receptors in the brain, as we learn from (Thomann *et al.*, 2024). Psilocin is a non-selective agonist at several serotonin receptor subtypes, particularly 5-HT_{2A}, 5-HT_{2C}, and 5-HT_{1A} receptors. These receptors are involved in regulating mood, perception, and cognition. The activation of the 5-HT_{2A} receptor is crucial for the psychedelic effects of psilocybin. In addition to its impact on serotonin receptors, research has shown that psilocybin can also alter brain activity and connectivity, particularly in the default-mode network (DMN), which includes regions such as the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus. This shift in brain activity is thought to contribute to the altered consciousness and emotional processing experienced by individuals who take psilocybin. Psilocin may also interact with other neurotransmitter systems, including glutamate, adding complexity to its pharmacological profile. These brain changes can affect physiological functions, including visual processing, decision-making, and heart rate.

PK (Pharmacokinetics)

ABSORPTION

As stated in (Thomann *et al.*, 2024), after oral administration, psilocybin is rapidly absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract. As it passes through the gut and liver, psilocybin is quickly metabolised into its active form, psilocin, through dephosphorylation. This process is facilitated by enzymes such as alkaline phosphatases and non-specific esterases. According to (Dodd *et al.*, 2023), the bioavailability of orally administered psilocybin, measured as the amount of psilocin that reaches the systemic circulation, is estimated to be around 52.7 ±

20.4%. This suggests that a significant portion of the administered dose becomes available to produce its pharmacological effects.

DISTRIBUTION

Once absorbed and converted into psilocin, the active metabolite is distributed throughout the body, including the brain, where it interacts with serotonin receptors to induce psychoactive and potentially therapeutic effects. Different studies provide varying data. Based on the research by (Badnjević and Gurbeta Pokvić, 2024, p.542) and (Singh *et al.*, 2019), it can be estimated that psilocin binds to plasma proteins at approximately 66%. The onset of effects after oral administration of psilocybin usually occurs within 20 to 50 minutes, with peak effects typically experienced around 60 to 90 minutes after ingestion. This relatively fast onset contributes to the acute nature of the psilocybin experience.

METABOLISM

As stated in (Thomann *et al.*, 2024), psilocin undergoes further metabolism primarily in the liver. The main metabolic pathway is glucuronidation, where psilocin is conjugated with glucuronic acid to form psilocin-O-glucuronide, an inactive metabolite easily excreted in the urine. Another significant metabolic process includes demethylation and oxidative deamination, likely mediated by monoamine oxidase (MAO), leading to 4-hydroxyindole-3-acetic acid (4-HIAA). The involvement of specific enzymes, such as UDP-glucuronosyltransferases (UGTs) in glucuronidation, and possibly cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzymes and MAO in other pathways, indicates a potential risk of drug interactions if psilocin is taken with substances that affect these enzymes.

EXCRETION

After analysing and reviewing the three articles I referred to (Raithatha *et al.*, 2023), (Thomann *et al.*, 2024) and (Singh *et al.*, 2019), I found that some studies report one range of values, while others suggest slightly different results. As I am not a scientist, I cannot be sure my interpretation is accurate. However, based on the information provided, I believe the range I've mentioned represents a reasonable and safe estimate. The values synthesise the findings from the articles, considering the different perspectives presented.

The primary route of excretion for psilocin and its metabolites is through the kidneys, with most compounds eliminated in the urine. A smaller amount may also be excreted in faeces and bile. The elimination half-life of psilocin, which is the time needed for its plasma concentration to decrease by half, ranges from approximately 1.4 to 2.0 hours. However, some studies report a wider range. The duration of psilocybin's subjective effects typically lasts between 4 and 6 hours but can vary from 3 to 12 hours depending on the dose and individual factors.

Safety information and side effects of the COMP360

As stated in (Amsterdam *et al.*, 2011), studies on psilocybin, the active compound in magic mushrooms, indicate that its use is generally considered safe, with mild side effects. However, unpredictable panic attacks and flashbacks remain a concern. The effects typically last between two and six hours, with some residual symptoms, such as sleep disturbances, persisting up to twelve hours. Users report relaxation, dizziness, euphoria, and visual alterations, though delusions and hallucinations can also occur. Anxiety is a common side effect, affecting around 32% of users. Some mushrooms contain phenylethylamine, which may cause cardiovascular effects such as tachycardia, though these reactions are rare.

A “bad trip” can involve severe anxiety, paranoia, and loss of reality, sometimes leading to accidents or self-harm. Though data on frequency is limited, bad trips are a leading cause of emergency room visits related to magic mushrooms. Symptoms may persist for days or weeks, and in some cases, chronic psychotic states can develop. The risk increases when mushrooms are combined with alcohol or other psychoactive substances. Individuals with pre-existing mental disorders, including schizophrenia, psychosis, or bipolar disorder, face a higher risk of psychological deterioration.

Based on the research conducted by (National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA), 2024) in controlled clinical settings, the risk of serious mental health effects is low. Still, outside of these environments, adverse outcomes are more likely. Psilocybin is contraindicated for individuals with significant psychiatric conditions. Physically, it can elevate blood pressure and heart rate, posing a risk for those with heart conditions. Nausea and vomiting are also possible side effects. While psilocybin does not cause physical dependence, users may develop a temporary tolerance.

As noted (Duerr, H. A., 2024), ensuring a supportive, supervised environment significantly reduces risks associated with magic mushroom use. In clinical trials, pure psilocybin (COMP360) is administered under strict monitoring. In a phase 2 PTSD study, the most common adverse effects were headache (50%), nausea (36.4%), and fatigue (27.3%), while suicidal ideation (9%) was transient and limited to participants with prior suicide attempts. Trial participants are screened for mental health and cardiovascular conditions, and discontinuation of psychotropic medications is usually required.

Clinical trials include psychological support through the Compass Psychological Support Model (CPSM), which focuses on preparation, psychoeducation, and integration. Overall, while psilocybin has a low risk of serious physical side effects, psychological risks remain, particularly in uncontrolled environments or among vulnerable individuals. Clinical research suggests that, with proper precautions, psilocybin can be used safely under controlled conditions.

Introduction to ICH Safety Guidelines

As we can read on the official website (ICH, 2025), The International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH) plays a pivotal role in shaping the global landscape of pharmaceutical development. Since its establishment in 1990, ICH has brought together regulatory authorities and the pharmaceutical industry to harmonise scientific and technical standards across regions. This collaboration has led to the creation of ICH guidelines, which ensure that medicines are developed, registered, and maintained in a way that prioritises safety, efficacy, and quality. These guidelines have become essential tools in the regulatory process and are adopted by an increasing number of authorities worldwide. As the pharmaceutical sector continues to evolve, ICH remains at the forefront, guiding the development of new medicines and promoting greater efficiency in the industry.

As stated on (ICH, 2009), The International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) has established a comprehensive suite of guidelines to ensure pharmaceutical products' safety, quality, and efficacy. The Safety Guidelines specifically address identifying and characterising potential risks associated with new drugs, including carcinogenicity, genotoxicity, and reproductive toxicity (ICH, 2025). ICH guideline M3(R2) provides specific recommendations regarding the scope and duration of non-clinical safety studies necessary to support human clinical trials and eventual marketing authorisation for pharmaceutical products. The overarching goals of these non-clinical evaluations are to thoroughly characterise any potential toxic effects of the drug, including identifying target organs, understanding the relationship between dose and toxicity, assessing the relevance of exposure levels, and determining the potential for these effects to be reversible.

ICH S7: Pharmacology Studies

Several preclinical studies are conducted to assess a drug's safety, including safety pharmacology studies and an assessment of the substance's potential to prolong the QT interval, which may be necessary for the drug's safety in humans. According to (ICH, 2000) and (ICH, 2005) guidelines, it is essential to examine the effect of the substance on three key systems of the body: the cardiovascular system, the central nervous system, and the respiratory system. These studies are necessary before the drug is administered to humans.

Safety pharmacology studies aim to identify potential adverse pharmacodynamic effects that may impact patient safety. These studies assess the effect of the substance on vital functions such as blood pressure, heart rate, ECG, motor activity, behavioural changes, coordination, sensory-motor reflexes, and body temperature, depending on the system being tested. In the case of the respiratory system, parameters such as respiratory rate, tidal volume, and oxygen saturation are evaluated. These studies, conducted per the principles of Good Laboratory Practice (GLP), help determine whether a substance can potentially cause adverse effects in these systems.

Specific studies on cardiac ventricular repolarisation are also carried out as part of the safety assessment. According to the (ICH, 2005) guideline, the test substance should be evaluated for the risk of prolonging the QT interval in the ECG, which can lead to ventricular arrhythmias, including torsades de pointes. For this purpose, both in vitro and in vivo studies are conducted to assess the effect of the substance on the ionic current flowing through the IKr channel and the QT interval in the ECG in animals. These studies, conducted by GLP, are essential to assess the risk the substance may pose to patients' health.

The results collected from these different tests are then analysed as part of an integrated risk assessment, which allows the prediction of the side effects that may occur during subsequent clinical trials. The methodology of these studies considers the substance's specific properties, its expected therapeutic effect, and the possible risks to humans. All these activities aim to ensure the highest possible level of safety before the drug is introduced for use in humans.

ICH S2 (R1): Genotoxicity Studies

The guideline on genotoxicity testing aims to determine the genotoxic potential of medicinal products for human use, which is a key element in the pre-market safety assessment of a drug. This assessment allows for identifying substances that may cause genetic damage, predicting potential carcinogenic risk and heritable mutagenic effects. The standard battery of genotoxicity tests includes in vitro and in vivo tests to assess mutagenicity and chromosomal damage.

The two equivalent options for genotoxicity testing are gene mutation tests in bacteria and tests assessing chromosomal damage. In the first option, a gene mutation test in bacteria, an in vitro cytogenetic test (such as a chromosomal aberration or micronucleus test), or a gene mutation test in mouse lymphoma cells is recommended. Additionally, in this option, an in vivo genotoxicity test should be performed, most often based on the assessment of chromosomal damage in rodent hematopoietic cells. The second option involves a bacterial gene mutation test and an in vivo genotoxicity assessment in two different tissues, with additional tests, such as a DNA strand break test in the liver.

Completing tests with negative results usually provides certainty of the absence of genotoxic activity. Still, positive results may require more detailed studies depending on the drug's therapeutic use. The guideline also notes that a comprehensive assessment of the safety of a preclinical drug requires other tests, such as general toxicity, reproductive toxicity, or pharmacokinetics.

The in vitro testing methodology includes tests such as the bacterial reverse mutation test (Ames test), which tests for the mutagenicity of the substance. In this case, the maximum dose is 5000 µg/plate, and for liquid substances, 5 µL/plate, provided that cytotoxicity does not occur. In addition, maximum concentrations of 1 mM or 0.5 mg/ml, whichever is lower, are used for tests on mammalian cells.

In vivo studies assess chromosomal damage in bone marrow or peripheral blood cells of rodents, as well as DNA strand breaks in the liver. The choice of dose depends on the type of study and may include three dose levels, with a recommended limit dose of 2000 mg/kg in short-term studies. An essential element in in vivo tests is the confirmation of the appropriate exposure of the target tissue to the tested substance, which is crucial for interpreting results, especially in cases of negative results.

In summary, the guideline defines the methodology and requirements for genotoxicity studies, which are the basis for assessing the risk of using new drugs in humans.

Recommended Non-Clinical Safety Studies for COMP360

After gaining a deeper understanding of how psilocybin affects the human body and the side effects it may cause, I have concluded that studying cardiotoxicity, neurotoxicity, respiratory safety, and genotoxicity in the context of psilocybin (COMP360) therapy is justified for several important reasons:

Cardiotoxicity: Psilocybin has the potential to affect the cardiovascular system, which may increase the risk of serious heart events, such as high blood pressure, an elevated heart rate, or even cardiac arrest, particularly in patients with existing heart conditions. It is essential to conduct studies in this area to understand better how psilocybin may impact the cardiovascular system, especially in those with a history of heart problems.

Neurotoxicity: Psilocybin acts on the central nervous system (CNS), and its use carries the risk of changes in behaviour, such as hallucinations, anxiety, paranoia, and potentially even alterations in brain structure if used excessively or over the long term. Research on neurotoxicity will help us determine if psilocybin therapy could cause permanent changes to the CNS or negatively affect the mental health of patients, particularly in those with mental health disorders like PTSD or treatment-resistant depression.

Respiratory Safety: Although the risk of breathing issues is low, anxiety, fear, or "bad trip" experiences can lead to breathing problems, such as hyperventilation or shortness of breath, especially during intense moments of a psychedelic experience. Therefore, it is essential to assess the potential respiratory risks of psilocybin, particularly in patients with a history of respiratory issues or high levels of anxiety.

Genotoxicity: Even if long-term therapy with COMP360 is not intended, it is essential to study the potential risk of mutagenicity and changes to DNA that may lead to the development of tumours. Since psilocybin affects neurotransmitters in the brain, it may also influence molecular processes in the body. Genotoxicity studies will help us understand whether psilocybin use is linked to damage to genetic material, which is crucial for ensuring the long-term safety of this drug.

In conclusion, these studies are vital to fully understanding the health risks associated with psilocybin and ensuring the safety of patients during therapy.

Conclusion

COMP360, based on synthetic psilocybin, is a promising alternative for the treatment of treatment-resistant depression (TRD) and other psychiatric disorders such as PTSD and obsessive-compulsive disorder. Clinical trials so far have shown significant improvement in depression symptoms, making COMP360 a strong candidate for a breakthrough in treating mental illnesses that are difficult to manage with traditional methods. In particular, studies suggest that combining psilocybin with psychological therapy brings long-term benefits, improving patients' quality of life.

From a pharmacodynamic perspective, psilocybin interacts strongly with serotonin receptors, leading to changes in brain activity and potential therapeutic effects. Pharmacokinetic analysis shows that it is absorbed quickly and has a relatively short half-life, which may influence the duration of its therapeutic effects.

Although psilocybin is still in the clinical development phase, its safety profile, based on strict protocols, suggests a low risk of serious side effects, especially in controlled conditions. However, it is essential to consider potential psychological risks, particularly when the substance is used without professional supervision.

Socrates said, "*I know that I know nothing*". This statement looks pretty accurate regarding psilocybin's history and my reflections. Socrates believed that the more we learn, the more we realise how little we know. While working on this assignment, I found myself asking even more questions. On a general level, I gained a better understanding of how the human body works and how different substances affect it. At the same time, I realised how incredibly complex this system is and how much remains to be discovered.

In the future, the development of COMP360 could transform the treatment of psychiatric disorders, especially for patients with TRD who do not respond to conventional medications. Final approval from regulatory authorities and further clinical trials will help explore the full potential of psilocybin as a psychiatric treatment.

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